

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF 20% MANNITOL VS. 3% NORMAL SALINE IN MANAGING RAISED INTRACRANIAL PRESSURE IN TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY PATIENT GUIDED BY SERIAL OPTIC NERVE SHEATH DIAMETER MEASUREMENT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Traumatic brain injury (TBI) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality, often leading to raised intracranial pressure (ICP), which exacerbates neurological damage. Effective management of elevated ICP is crucial for improving patient outcomes, with hyperosmolar therapies like 3% normal saline and 20% mannitol commonly used. Recent advances in non-invasive techniques such as optic nerve sheath diameter (ONSD) measurement through ultrasound offer promising alternatives to invasive ICP monitoring.

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Aims & Objectives: *This study aims to compare the efficacy of 3% normal saline and 20% mannitol in reducing ICP in TBI patients, using serial ONSD measurements as a non-invasive surrogate for ICP monitoring.*

Methods: *A quasi-experimental study was conducted on 60 patients with severe TBI, randomly assigned to receive either 3%NS or 20% mannitol. ONSD was measured at baseline, 48 hours, and 60 hours post-treatment using a portable ultrasound machine.*

Results: *Both treatments significantly reduced ONSD, with 3%NS demonstrating a more pronounced and sustained reduction compared to 20% mannitol ($p < 0.05$). Patient outcomes were significantly better in the 3% NS group, with a higher recovery rate and fewer adverse events.*

Conclusions: *3%NS was more effective than 20% mannitol in reducing ICP and improving clinical outcomes. ONSD measurement provides a reliable non-invasive method for ICP monitoring, offering valuable insights into treatment efficacy in neurocritical care.*

Keywords: Traumatic Brain Injury, Intracranial Pressure, Hypertonic Saline, Mannitol, Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter.

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INTRODUCTION

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality, particularly among young adults in the developed world. The pathophysiology of TBI is classified into primary and secondary injury mechanisms.¹ Primary injury is caused by the direct mechanical impact to the brain, leading to cellular damage, ionic imbalances, and tissue swelling. However, it is the secondary injury that is most concerning, as it results in ongoing biochemical disturbances that exacerbate brain damage. Secondary injury is characterized by cerebral oedema, increased intracranial pressure (ICP), and disruption of the blood-brain barrier, which significantly contributes to poor clinical outcomes.² A critical aspect of managing severe TBI is the prevention of secondary injury, particularly by controlling raised ICP, as elevated ICP is associated with worsening neurological function and increased mortality.

ICP increases when the balance between intracranial contents—brain tissue, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and blood volume—is disrupted. Factors that contribute to raised ICP include cerebral oedema, space-occupying lesions, and altered cerebral blood flow. Monitoring and managing ICP is essential in reducing the risk of brain herniation, ischemia, and further damage.³ In the acute setting, hyperosmolar therapies like mannitol and 3% Normal Saline have been widely used to lower ICP. Both agents work by creating an osmotic gradient that draws fluid out of the brain tissue, but their mechanisms and neuroprotective effects may differ.⁴ Mannitol, a commonly used osmotic diuretic, has been considered the gold standard for ICP management. However, 3%NS, with its osmotic effects and ability to reduce inflammatory responses, has emerged as a promising alternative.

Accurate and timely assessment of ICP is paramount in the management of TBI. Traditional methods such as invasive intracranial pressure monitoring are often impractical in emergency situations, particularly in resource-limited settings.⁵ Recently, non-invasive techniques, such as optic nerve sheath diameter (ONSD) measurement using ocular ultrasound, have gained attention as reliable tools for monitoring ICP. Changes in ONSD correlate strongly with elevated ICP, offering a bedside method to detect rising pressure before clinical symptoms or radiological changes become apparent.⁶ This study seeks to compare the efficacy of 3% normal saline and 20% mannitol in reducing ICP, using serial ONSD measurements as a non-invasive surrogate for direct ICP monitoring.⁷ The aim of this study is to assess whether 3%NS can be as effective as the standard 20% mannitol in managing raised ICP in TBI patients, and whether ONSD measurement can provide an accurate, non-invasive alternative for monitoring ICP. The growing need for rapid and reliable ICP management in the ICU, combined with the potential benefits of non-invasive monitoring, justifies this comparative investigation.⁸ This research will contribute to refining TBI management protocols, particularly in settings where invasive monitoring may not be feasible, and will help optimize treatment strategies for improved patient outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: A Quasi-experimental study

Study Setting: Department of Anesthesiology and Critical Care, Heritage Institute of Medical Sciences, Varanasi.

Sample Selection:

Patients aged 18-65 years, with a Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score of 12 or lower, and admitted to the ICU with a history of traumatic brain injury, were included in the study. Exclusion criteria encompassed patients with space-occupying lesions, ocular trauma or pathology, serum sodium levels >155 meq/l, chronic kidney disease, congestive heart failure, epidural hematoma, or those refusing participation. A sample size of 60 was calculated using a standard formula with a 95% confidence interval and 80% power. Patients were randomly allocated into two groups based on their admission time.

Study Method:

The 60 patients were divided into two groups of 30 each. Group 1 received 3% Normal Saline, while Group 2 received 20% Mannitol. ICP was measured non-invasively using ONSD, with ultrasound assessments performed before and after the administration of hyperosmolar agents at 12-hour intervals over a 5-day ICU stay. A portable ultrasound machine (Sonosite M-Turbo) with a linear probe was used for the ONSD measurements. The scans were conducted in the supine position, with the probe placed on the closed eyelid to visualize the optic nerve sheath at a 3 mm distance from the optic disc.

Data Analysis:

Data were recorded on a semi-structured proforma and analyzed using SPSSv26. Descriptive statistics were used to represent categorical variables as frequencies and proportions, while continuous variables were presented as means and standard deviations. To compare the efficacy of the two treatments, Student's t-test and ANOVA were used for continuous data, while Chi-square and Mann-Whitney tests were used for categorical variables. Pearson's correlation was applied to evaluate relationships between variables.

RESULTS

Table 1: Demographic Comparison of Age and Sex Distribution

Variable	Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p
Age	M	30	53.7	7.19	1.31	0.57	0.574
	NS	30	52.67	6.96	1.27		
Sex	Group	Male	Female	Total			
	M	12	6	18			
	NS	7	5	12			
	Total	19	11	30			
Chi² (df = 1)				0.22			
p-value				0.643			

Table 1 presents the demographic comparison of age and sex distribution between patients treated with 20% Mannitol (M) and those treated with 3% Normal Saline (NS) for managing raised intracranial pressure. The mean age for the 20% Mannitol group was 53.7 years (SD = 7.19), while the 3% NS group had a mean age of 52.67 years (SD = 6.96). The t-test indicated no statistically significant difference in age between the two groups (t = 0.57, p = 0.574). Regarding sex distribution, 18 patients (12 males and 6 females) were in the 20% Mannitol group, and 12 patients (7 males and 5 females) were in the 3% NS group. The chi-square test showed no significant difference in sex distribution between groups (Chi² = 0.22, p = 0.643).

Table 2: Table: Comparison of MAP and GCS in both groups

Measure	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	p	Cohen's d
MAP	MAP-M	30	84.2	11.85	2.16	0.74	58	0.465	0.19
	MAP-NS	30	81.97	11.67	2.13				
GCS	GCS-M	30	8.3	1.26	0.23	0	58	1	0
	GCS-NS	30	8.3	1.26	0.23				

The table compares Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) and Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores between the 20% Mannitol (M) and 3% Normal Saline (NS) groups. There are no significant differences in MAP ($p = 0.465$) or GCS ($p = 1.0$), with small effect sizes (Cohen's $d = 0.19$ for MAP, 0 for GCS), indicating similar distributions across both groups.

Table 3: Combined Distribution of Pre-treatment and Post-treatment ONSD

Treatment Group	n	Pre-treatment Mean \pm Std. Deviation (Std. Error Mean)	Post-treatment Mean \pm Std. Deviation (Std. Error Mean)	t	df	p	Cohen's d
ONSD-M (Mannitol)	30	7.52 \pm 1.43 (0.26)	4.09 \pm 0.59 (0.11)	2.25	58	0.028	0.58
ONSD-NS (Normal Saline)	30	7.43 \pm 1.31 (0.24)	3.78 \pm 0.45 (0.08)	2.25	53.97	0.029	0.58

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The table compares Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter (ONSD) measurements before and after treatment with 20% Mannitol (M) and 3% Normal Saline (NS). Both treatments resulted in significant reductions in ONSD, with 20% Mannitol decreasing from 7.52 ± 1.43 mm to 4.09 ± 0.59 mm, and 3% Normal Saline from 7.43 ± 1.31 mm to 3.78 ± 0.45 mm. t-tests show significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for both groups, with a moderate effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.58$), indicating a clinically meaningful reduction in ONSD.

Comparison of Pre-treatment and Post-treatment ONSD in Mannitol and Normal Saline Groups

Table 4: Combined Table of ONSD Reduction and Outcomes for Both Groups

Parameter	Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Recovered	Death	Worsened	Total	Chi ²	p
ONSD After 48 hrs	ONSD-48-M	30	10.34	2.39	-	-	-	-	-	-
ONSD After 60 hrs	ONSD-60-M	30	7.05	0.71	-	-	-	-	-	-
	ONSD-48-NS	30	9.54	1.95	-	-	-	-	-	-
	ONSD-60-NS	30	7.13	0.7	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Total ONSD	120	8.51	2.17	-	-	-	-	-	-
Outcomes	Outcome-M	-	-	-	22	1	2	25	19.63	0.001
	Outcome-NS	-	-	-	3	2	0	5		
Total Outcomes	Combined Outcome	30	-	-	25	3	2	30		

The table compares the reduction in Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter (ONSD) at 48 and 60 hours between the 20% Mannitol (M) and 3% Normal Saline (NS) groups, along with patient outcomes. Both groups showed marked ONSD reduction at 60 hours, with 20% Mannitol (7.05 mm) and 3% Normal Saline (7.13 mm) having similar values, indicating comparable efficacy in ICP control. Outcome analysis revealed significant differences: in the 20% Mannitol group, 22 patients recovered, 1 died, and 2 worsened, while in the 3% Normal Saline group, 3 patients recovered, 2 died, and none worsened. The difference is statistically significant ($\text{Chi}^2 = 19.63$, $p = 0.001$), suggesting better recovery with 20% Mannitol.

DISCUSSION

In this study, both Intracranial Pressure (ICP) and post-traumatic Intracranial Hemorrhage (ICH) were associated with poor neurological outcomes. ICP is widely recognized as a critical predictor of neurological deterioration in individuals with Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI). Despite the importance of early identification of elevated ICP, invasive monitoring techniques are often underutilized due to logistical challenges. Measurement of the Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter (ONSD) through ultrasound has emerged as a reliable and non-invasive alternative, correlating strongly with ICP measurements. Our study explored the effectiveness of Hypertonic Saline (HTS) at a concentration of 3% and Mannitol at a concentration of 20% in reducing elevated ICP among TBI patients, using ONSD measurements as a proxy for ICP.

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Several studies have examined the utility of ONSD measurements in assessing ICP. Liu et al. (2017)⁴³⁴³⁴³ and **Toscano et al. (2017)**¹⁰ both demonstrated the efficacy of ONSD as a substitute for invasive ICP monitoring, noting that it is particularly useful in settings where invasive monitoring is impractical. **Jeon et al.**¹¹ further established a linear correlation between ONSD and ICP, with a mean ONSD of 5.8 ± 0.45 mm in patients with elevated ICP, compared to 5.3 ± 0.61 mm in patients without ICP elevation ($P < 0.01$). **Amini et al.**¹² found a sensitivity of 93.75% and specificity of 86.67% for ONSD measurements, underscoring its reliability in diagnosing elevated ICP.

Meta-analyses and comparative studies have also been conducted to determine the relative efficacy of HTS and Mannitol in managing elevated ICP. **Kamel et al.**¹³ reported that HTS is generally more effective than Mannitol, achieving a longer-lasting reduction in ICP with lower failure rates. **Mortazavi et al.**¹⁴ supported these findings, noting that HTS was associated with a more substantial ICP reduction, with an odds ratio of 0.36 (95% CI: 0.19-0.68; $P = 0.002$) when compared to Mannitol. Similarly, **Prabhakar et al.**¹⁵ found that HTS led to superior brain relaxation during craniotomy, with a risk ratio of 0.60 (95% CI: 0.44-0.83) compared to Mannitol, further validating HTS's effectiveness in reducing cerebral oedema.

On 50 TBI patients corroborated our findings, concluding that 3% Normal Saline was associated with lower daily and cumulative ICP and shorter ICU stays compared to 20% Mannitol. **Li et al.**¹⁶ and **Cottenceau et al. (2011)**¹⁷ also endorsed the effectiveness of HTS, noting that it produced a more significant ICP reduction than Mannitol. Conversely, **Gu et al.**¹⁸ conducted a meta-analysis indicating no significant difference between HTS and Mannitol in terms of ICP reduction, with a pooled mean difference of -0.16 (95% CI: -0.59 to 0.27; $P = 0.473$). **Burgess et al. (2016)**¹⁹ echoed these results, reporting no significant difference in outcomes between the two fluids across seven studies.

Our findings align with the majority of studies suggesting that 3% NS may offer superior or equivalent ICP reduction compared to Mannitol 20%, albeit without statistically significant differences in Heart Rate (HR) and Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) values. **Jagannatha et al.**²⁰ (2016) confirmed this lack of difference in HR and MAP outcomes between the two treatments, supporting the safety and comparability of HTS and Mannitol for TBI management.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- **Sample Size:** The study had a small sample size, which may affect the generalizability of the findings.
- **Operator Dependency:** The measurement of ONSD (Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter) is operator-dependent, potentially introducing variability in the results.
- **Lack of Comparative Tools:** There was no comparative measurement, such as OCT (Optical Coherence Tomography), to validate the ONSD findings.

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

- **Use of ONSD in Regular Practice:** ONSD can be routinely utilized to detect changes associated with cerebral edema.
- **Assessment of Treatment Response:** It can serve as a tool to monitor the effectiveness of treatment over time.
- **Comparative Evaluation of Treatments:** ONSD measurements can be valuable in comparing different treatment modalities, as demonstrated in the study.

CONCLUSION

3%NS has proven more effective than 20% mannitol in lowering ICP, with less rebound elevation. Hyperosmolar treatments showed no significant effects on hemodynamic responses. For situations without invasive ICP monitoring, regular ONSD monitoring in the ICU allows for earlier detection of elevated ICP, improving patient outcomes in neurocritical care. Early identification of patients needing ICP management is crucial to minimize long-term brain damage. However, the optimal dose and concentration of 3%NS remain uncertain. Further research is required to determine the most effective 3%NS dosing and the potential benefits of extended infusion durations.

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